

A short history of the Subtle System *(in India)*

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In the *Brhadaranyaka Upanishad*, one of the early upanishads, is the first presentation of multiple pathways of vital energy in the subtle body:

When he is deeply asleep, when he knows nothing at all, he moves along the seventy-two thousand channels called *Hita* from the heart to the citadel of the heart. Having moved quietly along them he lies down in the citadel. He lies there as a young prince or a great king or a great Brahmana would lie on reaching the utmost ecstasy of bliss. (2.1.19)

Here the channels are called *Hita*, a term also found in early Sanskrit medical texts, but not used in later yoga texts where *Nadi* is the preferred term.

Another early expression of the subtle system appears in the *Chandogya Upanishad*, in which

one of the channels emanating from the heart penetrates the crown of the head enabling a man to reach the immortal:

There are a hundred and one arteries of the heart; one of them penetrates the crown of the head; moving upwards by it a man reaches the immortal. (8.6.6)

A similar verse appears in the *Katha Upanishad*.

It is in the *Katha Upanishad*, possibly dated as early as the fifth century BCE, that we find the first description of yoga and the need for thoughtless awareness:

The wise who, by means of meditation on his Self, recognises the Ancient, who is difficult to be seen, who has entered into the dark, who is hidden in the cave, who dwells in the abyss, as God, he indeed leaves joy and sorrow far behind. (1.2.12)

Ruff (2002) is of the view that Yoga as a system is first expounded in the *Maitrayantya Upanishad*, dating this text to the second century BCE.

The necessity for thoughtless awareness is also emphasised by Patanjali several hundred years later in his *Yoga Sutras* which are a summation of

all the knowledge of yoga known at that time (variously dated between 2nd – 3rd century BCE and 2nd – 3rd century CE). Patanjali defines yoga in the first sutra as being ‘the cessation of the turnings of thoughts’ (1.2).

In the *Katha Upanishad* is the first mention of the ancient tree whose roots grow upwards:

There is that ancient tree, whose roots grow upward and whose branches grow downward;- that indeed is called the Bright, that is called Brahman, that alone is called the Immortal . All worlds are contained in it, and no one goes beyond. This is that. (2.6.1)

This simile is repeated in later texts and later also in the songs of the Sahajiya Buddhists (8th – 10th centuries) and the bhakta yogis of the nirgun tradition (13th – 17th centuries).

The *Mandukya Upanishad*, written by the sage Mandukya and contained in the *Arthava-Veda*, is the source of the theory of the four states of consciousness: waking, dreaming, deep sleep, and the fourth state, *turiya*, or enlightenment. Here also we find an early explanation of the sacred AUM:

It is the soul; it should be discerned. This is the soul in regard to the word AUM and its parts. The parts are the letters, and the letters are its parts: A U M.

The waking state common to all is the letter A, the first part, from "attaining" or from being first. Whoever knows this attains all desires and becomes first.

The sleeping state, the bright, is the letter U, the second part, from "uprising" or from being in between. Whoever knows this rises up in knowledge and is balanced; no one ignorant of God is born in that family.

The deep-sleep state, the wise, is the letter M, the third part, from "measure" or from being the end. Whoever knows this measures everything and reaches the end.

The fourth is without a letter, the incommunicable, the end of evolution, good, non-dual.

Thus AUM is the soul.

As Shankara wrote a commentary on the *Manukya Upanishad* and on an earlier commentary by Gaudapada, the dating has to be pre-7th century CE.

The later *Mandalabrahmana Upanishad* unusually proposes five states of consciousness, adding a state "that is beyond the fourth state" (quoted by Ruff 2002:155).

In the later *Brahma Vidya Upanishad* (9th – 11th centuries) there is a description of the ‘Brahman power’ ascending to the crown of the head:

Yet one, like a pointed flame subtle, like lotus-fibre, shines through the Sun-like cerebral artery and penetrates the Aum. Through the Sun and seventy-two thousand arteries, breaks through the top of the head [*murdham*] and remains as bringer of blessings to all – pervading the whole Universe. (11-12)

It is in the *Varaha Upanishad* that we find a comprehensive description of the ascent of the Kundalini from the Muladhara through the chakras to the top of the head:

In the centre of the anus and the genitals, there is the triangular Muladhara. It illumines the seat of Shiva of the form of Bindu. There is located the Parasakti named Kundalini. From that seat, Vayu arises. From that seat, Agni becomes increased. From that seat, Bindu originates and Nada becomes increased. From that seat, Hamsa is born. From that seat, Manas is born. The six Chakras beginning with Muladhara are said to be the seat of Sakti (Goddess). From the neck to the top of the head is said to be the seat of Sambhu (Shiva). To the Nadis, the body is the support (or vehicle); to Prana, the Nadis are the support; to Jiva, Prana is the dwelling place; to Hamsa, Jiva is the support. (5.50-54)

Here also we find use of the term *nadis* for the channels.

The *Ksurika Upanishad* recognises 101 *nadis* and identifies the three main *nadis* of *ida*, *pingala*, and *sushumna*. It is possible that the first use of *sushumna* for the central channel can be found in the *Maitrayaniya Upanishad*. (Ruff 2002:223)

Six-centre systems

As we have seen, the earlier Upanishads use a variety of terminology to describe the pathways and the vital points of the body, and these notions are also found in the Sanskrit medical texts. Ruff (2002) is of the view that the term *chakra* (also transcribed into English as *cakra*), referring to an energy centre in the subtle body, probably first occurs in the *Kaulajnananirnaya* (9th century CE) which also provides the earliest extant systematic presentation of the six *chakra* system. Other *chakra* systems also existed such as the four-centre system found in the Buddhist tantras, the five-centre system found, along with the six centres, in the *Kubjikatmata Tantra*. The *Kaulajnananirnaya* uses both six-*chakra* and eleven-*chakra* systems.

The six-centre system is first mentioned in the century Sanskrit drama *Malati Madhava* of Bhavabhuti, who is variously dated from c.500 to 8th century CE. Primarily a love story, this play contains incidental descriptions of the practices of the Kapalika Saivite sect of ascetics.

The six-chakra system was adopted by several groups of ascetics, notably by Gorakhnath and the Nath yogis. Over time this became the dominant system in yogic texts.

Tantras and other sources

The knowledge of the ascent of the Kundalini through the *nadis* also appears in other forms of literature, notably the *tantras*, or instruction manuals, which appear both in the (Hindu) yogic tradition and in the Buddhist tradition, from the 4th century CE.

The *Sarvasiddhantasamgraha* (9th - 10th CE) also mentions the three main *nadis* of *ida*, *pingala*, and *sushumna*.

Sankara (variously dated as 7th – 8th centuries CE) refers to the ascending *Kundalini* in several of his works, notably in the *Saundarya-Lahari*:

Thou art diverting Thyself, in secrecy with Thy Lord, in the thousand-petaled lotus [*Sahasrara*], having pierced through the Earth situated in the Muladhara, the Water in the Manipura [*Nabhi*], the Fire abiding in the Swadisthana, the air in the heart [*Anahat*], the Ether above [*Vishuddhi*], and Manas between the eyebrows [*Agnya*] and thus broken through the entire Kula path [*Sushumna nadi*]

In South India, in a similar time-frame, namely 6th – 8th centuries, this knowledge is contained in the work of the Tamil siddhis, the best-known of whom is Thirumoolar. His *Thirumanthiram* contains instructions, albeit cryptic, on how to raise the Kundalini through the subtle system from Mooladhara to Sahasrara, thus achieving *yoga*.

When the great Buddhist monasteries of north Indian first began to be attacked and destroyed by the invading Moghuls from the 8th century onwards, some of the Buddhist monks chose to escape to the hills and to the river deltas where they joined other ascetics and yogis. These Sahajiya Buddhists have left songs describing the

Sahaja state, and referring to the chakras and nadis using a variety of imagery, often drawn from the nature around them, which we will discuss in more detail later in this essay.

Naths

Originating in the eleventh century, successive generations of Nath yogis maintained the tradition of kundalini awakening through rigorous asceticism and hatha yoga practices. Their sacred texts contain detailed knowledge of the chakras and nadis of the subtle system, as in the *Siddha-Siddhanta-Paddhati*, which is attributed to Gorakhnath. In the *Kaulajnananirnaya*, attributed to Matsyendranath, we find mention of the higher chakras, namely Sahasrara and beyond.

Gorakhnath's disciple, Gahininath took as his disciple a young boy, Nivritti, who in turn became the guru to his brothers, Jnaneshwara and Sopandev, and sister, Muktabai, and their close friend, Namdev. It is Jnaneshwara who provides a detailed description of the awakening of the Kundalini in the language of the ordinary people in the sixth chapter of his Marathi commentary on

the *Gita*, known as the *Jnaneshwari*, written in the 1280s. Muktabai and their close friend Namdev also referred to the subtle system and the ascent of the Kundalini in their songs, but used more oblique terminology. In one extraordinary song, Muktabai sings of the *ant* rising to the *Sun* to describe the ascent of the Kundalini to the Sahasrara:

An ant [*Kundalini*] flew to the sky and swallowed the sun
Another wonder - a barren woman had a son.
A scorpion went to the underworld
And the Shesh Nag [*thousand-headed serpent*] fell at its feet
A fly gave birth to a kite [*bird*]
Having seen it all, Mukta smiled.

Namdev, in one of his Marathi songs, also describes the ascent of the Kundalini:

in the beginning
is the ant [*Kundalini*]
mouth of the triple river [*the three nadis*]
is the mouth of the ant

in darkness
is the ant
in flames a wick of water
lights a lamp of soot

in the wake of the ant
all of the sky follows
the world of our making's her dropping

i pursue that ant
i, vishnudas nama
unlock the ant with my guru

Around 1300 CE, Namdev moved north to the Punjab where he continued to compose songs with hidden yogic meanings, these being in an early form of Hindi. In one song he notes that

Moving the sun to the moon,
Making firm the mind, the breath, the spinal column,
effortlessly I rose through the Sushumna [*central nadi*]
to the star-cluster [*Sahasrara chakra*] thus slaying
desire.

Eknath (1533-1599) was a Maratha-speaking saint who restored Jnneshwara's description of the Kundalini to the *Jnaneshwari* after it had been removed by the brahmin-scholars. His famous song *Jogawa* is an invocation to the Mother Kundalini to rise and grant self-realisation, best expressed in the chorus:

Jogawa Magen, Aicha Jogawa
Ai Ude G'ambe Ude!

Ude, Ude, Ude, Ude, Ude, Ude, Wo!

Mother, we ask for Self-realisation
So you rise, O Mother Kundalini, You rise!
Rise, rise, rise, rise, rise, rise, Ho!

Bengal and the Sahajiya tradition

In 16th century Bengal the ascent of the awakened Kundalini through the chakras is described in a Sanskrit text known as the *Satcakranirupana* (c.1577). The writer, one Purnanand Swami, begins his text by stating:

Now I speak of the first sprouting shoot of complete realization of the Brahman, which is to be achieved, according to the tantras, by means of the six chakras and so forth in their proper order.

Of particular interest in this text is the description of the Sahasrara and beyond in verses 44-49:

The Saivas call it [*the Sahasrara*] the abode of Siva; the Vaisnavas call it Parama Purusa; others again, call it the place of Hari-Hara. Those who are filled with a passion for the Lotus feet of the Devi call it the excellent abode of the Devi; and other great sages call it the pure place of the Prakrti-Purusa.

There are other ways of describing the pathways and energy centres of the subtle body, and the use of similes with the natural world are found throughout the Sahajiya tradition in Bengal down the centuries. The terminology of a river system is used to envision the inner subtle body. Thus mentions can be found of the banks of the river, of the use of boats to cross to the other side of the river, often moving with or against the current; and also to the movement of energies as fluids along the winding rivers, past villages and into a series of inner (enchanted) ponds.

In the *Amrtaratnavali* of Mukunda-dasa (c.1600 CE), a text of over 300 couplets rich in metaphors and Bengali cultural references, there are references to inner ponds, such as the four ponds to be found within the heart, mastery of which enables the seeker to “reach the other shore” (v.96-98). Also to landing-stairs, connected to the ‘path of the village leader’ (guru?) (v.164). The goal of the seeker is therefore to travel along the Viraja River to reach the village of Sahajapur:

This dharma is the purest, without division or simple lust (*kama*).

The abode (*dhama*) beyond the heavenly Viraja River is transcendent.

Along the far shores of the Viraja River is The Land
(*desakhana*).

Sahajapur is that Village (*grama*) which is called Eternal
Bliss (*sadananda*). (v41-42). (Hayes 2002).

Sufis and yogis

The knowledge of the subtle system was certainly passed from yogis to sufis, as this description from the 16th century Bengali sufi, Saiyid Sultan of Chittagong (now in Bangladesh) shows:

Ingala and *pingala* are the two nerves running by the two sides of the spinal chord and looking like two creeping plants hanging by the two sides of a tree. The nerve *ingala* in the right may be compared with the sun, and the *pingala* in the left resembles the moon. The *ingala* is the flow of the Ganges and the *pingala* that of the Jamna. The nerve running between the god and the demon is called *Susumna*. These three meet at a point which is regarded by the wise as the confluence of the three sacred rivers. [*Hamsa*]

Shah Abdul Latif (1689-1752), a sufi, who lived in Sind (now in Pakistan), has eloquently

described his meetings with the yogis in several verses:

In the world are yogis who worship light:
In the world are yogis who worship fire.
Without the holy men who lit the fire, the holy men, I
cannot live.
I was asleep on my couch: a deep sigh awoke me.
Without the holy men who woke me up, the holy men, I
cannot live. (Sorley 1940:348)

That these were Nath yogis is clear from another
verse:

If you want to be a yogi, follow the guru, forget all
desires, and proceed to Hinglaj.
The yogis respond to an ancient call that was given even
before Islam;
They have given up everything, to be one with
Gorakhnath. (Malkani 1984)

Shah Latif ultimately was given realisation by an
unnamed yogi who became his guru:

In this life we enjoyed a rare boon – the company of a
Yogi; the one, with whom we had a spiritual tie, revealed
himself to us.

In the neighbouring Punjab, the sufi Bullhe Shah (1680-1758) had his realisation from a yogi, as this verse makes clear:

Ranjha [*the Lord*] has come as a yogi
It is wonderful, Ranjha has come as a yogi.
The eyes of this Yogi, in wide sockets
Plunge over the victims like falcons
All the sorrows end when He comes in sight
My eyes have realised the dearest Lord.
What is the sign of this Yogi?
He has rings in his ears and the coloured string around
his neck. ...
I shall serve him with all my heart. (Kohli 1987:73)

A later sufi from Sind, Sachal Samarst (1739-1832) was given realisation by a yogi:

I recognised the yogi who of his own accord entered my abode. He had dressed himself in the garb of an ascetic as an artful device. He had long yogic tresses and his body was smeared with ash. His flute's melody entranced my soul. God had brought about this union between me and the yogi. For him I have now sprinkled perfume and musk. It was he who revealed to me the entire mystery. (Advani 1971:25)

This yogi is said to have been Vishivanath, who lived on the Hindukush mountain in northwest Sind.

Another sufi from Sind with yogic connections was Sami (1743-1850) who describes the subtle inner body as a series of houses within house:

Sami in this house there is another dwelling
And within that dwelling is another residence
In that residence is He that is houseless
Unreached by senses, speech or mind
Pure, indefinable, ever serene
The Guru has revealed this eternal glory. (Ajwani
1970:131)

This description reminds this writer of the typology used by the 16th century Spanish Christian nun, Theresa of Alvila in her book, *The Inner Castle*.

Mention should also be made of the *Lataif*, spiritual concepts in Sufism sometimes associated with the physical body. Whilst attributions of Lataif to specific parts of the physical body can be found in Sufi writings, not all Sufis who use the lataif compare them to the chakras of the yogic subtle body. Lizzio (2007) maintains that the Naqshbandi sufis regard the

lataif as having no fixed location and could be anywhere in the physical body, with the possible exception of the lataif for the heart. Harvat (1988) however gives six lataif and their locations in the physical body as used in the Mujaddidiyya branch of the Naqshbandi, named after the 17th century Sufi, Ahmad Sirhindi Mujaddid.

Harvat (1988) proposes that the Lataif are first found in the writings of the Turkestani Sufi, Najmuddin Kubra (1145-1220), founder of the Kubrawiyya order; and developed more fully in the writings of the Persian Sufi, Alaoddawleb Semnani (13th-14th century).

In India the lataif become associated with the chakras of the Nath yogis, as noted above. An early practitioner of this integration was Mohammad Ghawth (16th century), a master of the Shattari order. A theory of the lataif as subtle spiritual centers is to be found in the writings of the Indian Sufi, Shah Waliullah of Delhi (1703-1762) (Hermansen 1988).

Conclusion

There are of course other theories of subtle body in the history of spirituality that could be mentioned, notably the Sefirot of the Jewish mystical tradition, the Kabbala. Also the inner alchemy of the Taoist tradition in China, and representations of the planets in the human body to be found in Renaissance Europe. However none of these typologies had much, if any, influence on mystics in India.

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